

Coordinated aqua molecules mediated phosphoester cleavage activity of a dimeric gadolinium(III)-acetate

Abhranil De^a, Sitangshu Shekhar Pradhan^b and Bhaskar Biswas*^a

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Raghunathpur College, Purulia-723 133, West Bengal, India

E-mail : mr.bbiswas@rediffmail.com, icbbiswas@gmail.com

^bDepartment of Physics, Midnapore College (Autonomous), Midnapore-721 101, West Bengal, India

Manuscript received 10 July 2017, accepted 26 August 2017

Abstract : In this present work, we report the synthesis and X-ray crystallographic characterization of a dimeric gadolinium(III)-acetate, $[\text{Gd}(\text{OAc})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1) (OAc = acetate). Single crystal X-ray diffraction study reveals that this gadolinium acetate dimer crystallises in triclinic system with $P\bar{1}$ space group and each of the Gd^{III} centres in 1 adopts tricapped trigonal prism geometry. The lattice aqua molecules in this dimer form a 8-membered cyclic tetrameric water cluster mediated by 3D crystalline architecture of Gd^{III} complex through strong $\text{O}\cdots\text{H}$ hydrogen bonding interaction along a axis in its crystalline phase and signify its supramolecular aspects in biology. On the other hand, presence of coordinated aqua molecules create considerable interest to investigate the cleavage efficacy of 1 towards phosphoester bond using (p -nitrophenyl)phosphate (pNPP) in aqueous DMF medium. Kinetic experiments for the hydrolytic cleavage of DNA-model pNPP were followed spectrophotometrically following the incremental absorbance at 415 nm under normal conditions at 25 °C. The hydrolytic cleavage of the phosphodiester bond proceeds with the pseudo-first order initial rate, $k_{\text{obs}} = 5.43 \times 10^{-4}$ and $5.38 \times 10^{-4} \text{ min}^{-1}$ for 48 h and 24 h respectively, and produces an inorganic phosphate and p -nitrophenolate as the final products of hydrolysis. So both types of aqua molecules (lattice and coordinated) have considerable significance on the perspective of material science and biological chemistry.

Keywords : Gadolinium(III), crystal structure, water cluster, phosphatase activity.

Introduction

Design and synthesis of coordination compounds consisting of lanthanoid ions have created huge appeal in coordination chemist for their wide spread physico-chemical properties and applications of industrial significance¹⁻³. The prime spectrum of the application of lanthanoid compounds mainly concerted in designing contrasting agents for magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)¹, luminescent probes², magnetic materials designing³, etc. which brings special attention in design and synthesis of such complexes to produce developed molecules in material science. Among the lanthanoid complexes, gadolinium(III) complexes have most significant contribution in designing MRI contrasting agents, photoactive materials and magnetic

materials for providing maximum seven unpaired electrons¹⁻³. The focus behind the formation of bridged dinuclear core of paramagnetic metal centres is not only to couple together to form large spin systems but is to achieve ferro- or ferrimagnetic coupling, more importantly the existence of dinuclear core as valuable metalloenzymes in this living world. Furthermore, the photo-physical properties for such core are very important in designing advance photoactive materials⁴⁻⁶. Although, extensive biophysical and mechanistic data has been accumulated during last few decades but the absolute understanding of rate of the reactions, and the corresponding enzyme-catalysed processes, is still a very demanding topic in bioinorganic reactions⁶⁻⁸. In our environment, organophosphorous

*Present address : Department of Chemistry, Surendranath College, Kolkata-700 009, India.

compounds, one of the most widely used pesticides, are known to be extremely vulnerable towards living systems for having their natural tendency to inhibit acetyl cholinesterase and prevent the normal functioning of nerve cells⁹. So degradation of organophosphate molecules through catalytic hydrolysis pathway using metal catalyst will be the principal purpose of this investigation. Metallo-enzyme that hydrolytically hydrolyzes the phosphoester bonds was initially thought to consist of a single Zn^{II} in its active site¹⁰, but more recent analysis by atomic absorption spectroscopy and X-ray anomalous scattering suggested that the active form of these enzymes contain binuclear metallic units with a combination of Zn^{II} and Fe^{II} likely¹⁰. The active site of phosphatase enzyme is typically surrounded by coordination environment of nitrogen and oxygen donor systems of histidine ligands and aspartate respectively for two divalent metal ions, and in general includes a bridging hydroxide ion^{11–15}. In most hydrolytic enzymes, a metal-hydroxide is suggested as the nucleophile in the key hydrolysis step, although exogenous alcohol moieties are also implicated^{16,17}. Examples of model systems with either or both a metal-OH and a metal-OR present, which are implicated in the mechanism, have been previously reported^{18–20}. Interestingly, a coordinated alcohol is a stronger nucleophile than a coordinated hydroxide^{19,21–26} and there is evidence that the coordinated alcohol is deprotonated at or below the same pH as a coordinated water molecule, particularly in the case of zinc(II) complexes²¹. Previously Werner Urland *et al.*^{27a}, Allan H. White *et al.*^{27b}, reported the crystal structure of the dinuclear Gd^{III}-acetate compound in terms of electron pair repulsion theory. Again, Catalina Ruiz-Perez *et al.*, already explored the magnetic aspects of isostructural gadolinium(III) complexes with carboxylate ligands^{27c} but here in we report a different synthetic strategy in the formation of a dimeric gadolinium(III)-acetate, the water cluster formed through lattice aqua molecules and its efficiency to cleave the phosphoester bond through intra-molecular nucleophilic attack by coordinated aqua molecule on phosphorous atom in an efficient manner with initial rate, $k_{\text{obs}} = 5.43 \times 10^{-4} \text{ min}^{-1}$.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and formulation :

The synthesis and structure is previously reported by different scientist groups. Ruiz-Perez *et al.*^{27c}, synthesized this digadolinium acetate by slow evaporation of 0.02 M ethanolic solution of gadolinium(III)-acetate hexahydrate at room temperature. Werner Urland *et al.*^{27a}, previously synthesized the compound, $[\{\text{Gd}(\text{OAc})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\}_2] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ by mixing of Gd₂O₃ with acetic acid while Allan H. White reported the crystal structure of the dinuclear Gd^{III}-acetate compound in terms of electron pair repulsion theory^{27b}. But, we have taken a different approach for the preparation of dinuclear Gd^{III} complex and this compound was synthesized by mixing of gadolinium(III) chloride with saturated aqueous NaOAc at refluxing condition (Scheme 1). The coordination geometry of **1** was determined by mainly single crystal X-ray diffraction study along with different spectroscopic and analytical techniques. The colourless crystals suitable for X-ray data collection were obtained by slow evaporation of resultant reaction mixture.

Scheme 1. Preparative route for the Gd^{III} complex (**1**).

Crystal structure of $[\text{Gd}(\text{OAc})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**1**) :

The X-ray structural determination of Gd^{III} complex shows that Gd^{III} centres adopt a tricapped trigonal prism geometry (Fig. 1) and this compound crystallizes in triclinic system with *P* $\bar{1}$ space group. We are not discussing extensively about the X-ray structure since, it was previously reported by few scientists²⁷. The crystallographic structural parameters of **1** are listed in Table 1. Selected bond lengths and angles are presented in Table 2, and the relevant hydrogen bonding parameters are summarized in Table S1.

Fig. 1. A ellipsoid view of dimeric gadolinium acetate (**1**) with atom numbering scheme (30% probability).

Table 1. Crystallographic refinement parameters of $[\text{Gd}(\text{OAc})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**1**)

Crystal parameters	1
Empirical formula	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_{18}\text{Gd}_2$
Formula weight	812.89
Temperature	100.0 K
Wavelength	0.71073 Å
Crystal system	Triclinic
Space group	$P\bar{1}$
Unit cell dimensions	$a = 8.8752(5)$ Å $\alpha = 92.159(2)^\circ$ $b = 9.2426(5)$ Å $\beta = 113.560(2)^\circ$ $c = 10.3812(6)$ Å $\gamma = 118.454(2)^\circ$
Volume	$658.22(7)$ Å ³
Z	2
Density (Calcd.)	2.051 Mg/m ³
Absorption coefficient	5.076 mm ⁻¹
F(000)	394
Reflections collected	12193
Independent reflections	4180
R(int)	0.031
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.09
R indices (all data)	$R_1 = 0.0202,$ $wR_2 = 0.0480$
Largest diff. peak and hole	1.32 and -1.85 e. Å ⁻³

Supramolecular aspects of tetrameric water cluster in 1 :

Very close inspection of crystal packing of dimeric

gadolinium acetate reveals that lattice aqua molecules in dimeric Gd^{III} -acetate have significant contribution in framing and assembling the tetra-unit Gd^{III} -acetate in solid state through strong $\text{O}\cdots\text{H}$ interactions along a axis to form 3D crystalline architecture (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2. Formation of 8-membered cyclic water tetramer through $\text{O}\cdots\text{H}$ interactions between lattice water.

The construction of hydrogen bonded association among the lattice aqua molecules along a axis leads to the formation of cyclic water tetramers (Fig. 2, Table S1). Among the lattice tetra-aqua molecules, H atoms of two aqua molecules (H9A, H9B) of identical symmetry behave as acceptors while oxygen atoms of other two aqua molecules of identical symmetry (O10) act as donor centres. This tetrameric water cluster is further solidified by a support of neutral acetate-bridged dimeric gadolinium(III) complex (Fig. 2). This new metal complex mediated 3D crystalline architecture consists of fused cyclic 8-membered water clusters through $\text{O}9\text{-H}9\text{B}\cdots\text{O}10$, $\text{O}9\text{-H}9\text{A}\cdots\text{O}10$ of 2.01 Å, 1.93 Å (Fig. 2). Furthermore, the chelating cum bridging acetate anions with coordinated aqua molecules serve as linkers in the tetrameric aggregation of the Gd^{III} -acetate (Table S1).

Table 2. Selected bond lengths (Å) and bond angles (°) for Gd^{III}-acetate compound

Bond lengths					
Gd1-O1	2.476(2)	Gd1-O4	2.4708(19)	Gd1-O8	2.358(2)
Gd1-O2	2.4217(18)	Gd-O5	2.3868(18)	Gd1-O5_a	2.5501(19)
Gd1-O3	2.451(2)	Gd1-O7	2.3777(18)	Gd1-O6_a	2.4621(17)
Bond angles					
O1-Gd1-O2	52.90(6)	O3-Gd1-O4	52.78(7)	O5-Gd1-O5_a	64.49(6)
O1-Gd1-O3	129.81(6)	O3-Gd1-O5	76.61(6)	O5-Gd1-O6_a	115.83(6)
O1-Gd1-O4	113.48(7)	O3-Gd1-O7	144.21(7)	O7-Gd1-O8	75.52(6)
O1-Gd1-O5	153.43(6)	O3-Gd1-O8	125.98(7)	O7-Gd1-C1	105.10(7)
O1-Gd1-O7	78.89(6)	O3-Gd1-C1	104.00(7)	O7-Gd1-C3	153.84(7)
O1-Gd1-O8	77.43(7)	O3-Gd1-C3	26.41(7)	O5_a-Gd1-O7	73.10(6)
O1-Gd1-C1	26.52(7)	O3-Gd1-O5_a	73.24(6)	O6_a-Gd1-O7	84.09(6)
O1-Gd1-C3	125.93(7)	O3-Gd1-O6_a	84.37(6)	O8-Gd1-C1	88.00(8)
O1-Gd1-O5_a	120.61(6)	O4-Gd1-O5	78.61(7)	O8-Gd1-C3	100.07(7)
O1-Gd1-O6_a	74.86(6)	O4-Gd1-O7	143.52(6)	O5_a-Gd1-O8	138.99(6)
O2-Gd1-O3	78.30(7)	O4-Gd1-O8	74.29(7)	O6_a-Gd1-O8	148.21(8)
O2-Gd1-O4	73.50(6)	O4-Gd1-C1	93.85(8)	C1-Gd1-C3	100.45(7)
O2-Gd1-O5	150.21(6)	O4-Gd1-C3	26.38(8)	O5_a-Gd1-C1	125.26(6)
O2-Gd1-O7	131.20(7)	O4-Gd1-O5_a	120.23(8)	O6_a-Gd1-C1	73.92(7)
O2-Gd1-O8	98.25(7)	O4-Gd1-O6_a	131.65(6)	O5_a-Gd1-C3	96.68(7)
O2-Gd1-C1	26.39(7)	O5-Gd1-O7	78.26(6)	O6_a-Gd1-C3	108.67(6)
O2-Gd1-C3	74.76(7)	O5-Gd1-O8	83.87(7)	O5_a-Gd1-O6_a	51.35(6)
O2-Gd1-O5_a	122.28(6)	O5-Gd1-C1	170.15(6)		
O2-Gd1-O6_a	77.08(6)	O5-Gd1-C3	75.62(6)		

Fig. 2. Formation of 8-membered cyclic tetrameric water cluster mediated by 3D crystalline architecture of Gd^{III} complex through O...H hydrogen bonding interaction along *a* axis.

Phosphatase activity of [Gd(OAc)₃(OH₂)₂]₂·2H₂O (1) and its mechanistic implications :

The hydrolytic cleavage efficiency of the Gd^{III}

complex towards pNPP in aqueous DMF was detected spectrophotometrically by monitoring the time evolution of *p*-nitrophenolate ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 415 \text{ nm}$) through a wavelength scan from 200 to 900 nm at 25 °C, containing 100 equivalents of substrate relative to the catalyst, until roughly 2% reaction conversion was reached. Changes in the spectral features of the Gd^{III} complex upon the addition of pNPP are shown in Fig. 3, where the spectra were recorded for 2 h at 12 min intervals.

The kinetics study was performed using the initial slope method, following the rate of increase in the absorption of the band at 415 nm corresponding to a rise of 4-nitrophenolate concentration. The initial first order rate constants, $k_{\text{obs}}(\text{min}^{-1}) = 5.43 \times 10^{-4}$ (Error = 9.067×10^{-6}) and 3.38×10^{-4} (Error = 6.754×10^{-6}) for the cleavage of pNPP were obtained directly from the plot of $\log [A_{\alpha}/(A_{\alpha}-A_t)]$ values versus time (Fig. 4) which were linear with $R^2 = 0.9958$

Fig. 3. Increase of 4-nitrophenolate band at 415 nm after addition of 100 equivalents of pNPP to $[\text{Gd}(\text{OAc})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**1**) in aq. DMF medium. The spectra were recorded after every 12 min. Inset : Abs vs time of the same solution.

Fig. 4. Initial rate determination for dimeric gadolinium acetate (**1**) after 24 h and 48 h using plot of time vs $\log [A_\alpha / (A_\alpha - A_t)]$.

and 0.9940 respectively. To confirm the non-catalytic properties of the ligand, control experiments were performed under identical reaction conditions in aqueous DMF medium and found non-responsive towards pNPP hydrolysis. We did not find enough scientific literatures to make a survey on the first order catalytic rates of reported Gd^{III} complexes with our dimeric Gd^{III} complex.

We have taken careful measure to propose the

cleavage mechanism of pNPP for our dimeric gadolinium(III) complex from the reported scientific literatures^{31–35}. It is seen that metal catalysts can take significant initiatives for catalytic cleavage of pNPP through Lewis acid activation, metal-nucleophile attack and leaving group activation (Scheme 3) and exhibit remarkably fast rates of phosphate hydrolysis.

Scheme 3. Different modes by which phosphates are activated by metal ions.

Rate of acceleration for catalytic phenomenon are observed when multiple assisting parameters are working concurrently^{28–32}. After rigorous review of the scientific literature, we propose the plausible catalytic cycles having reasonably good agreement with our kinetic result. The generation of nucleophile from coordinated aqua molecules at the metal centres in the reaction medium remains the fundamental aspect in this catalysis which later follows the attack of metal bound nucleophile on phosphorous atom as a representative mechanism (Scheme 4).

In aqueous DMF solution, the dimeric Gd^{III} complex actually gets dissociated and the Gd^{III} species are extensively solvated during this period. pH of the solution at that time became lower (pH 4.1) since bridging acetate molecules produced acetic acid in solution. pH measurements of the dimeric complex in solution further consolidates its solution instability. Incorporation of pNPP to the coordination sphere of Gd^{III} complex is probably occurred in a monodentate fashion through phosphate-oxygen and possibility of $\text{O}\cdots\text{H}$ interactions between anionic oxide ($\text{P}-\text{O}^-$) ion with H atom of the coordinated aqua molecule further support this fact. At this stage, the coordinated aqua molecule deprotonates to yield a hydroxide ion as the potent nucleophile leading to an intermediate which

Scheme 4. Plausible mechanistic pathway for pNPP hydrolysis promoted by Gd^{III} complex.

is further consolidated in ESI-MS study as a major signal at an m/z of 590.24. It is followed by the formation of an organophosphorus intermediate by nucleophilic substitution reaction with the concomitant expulsion of 4-nitrophenolate ion. It then gradually breaks down into the active Gd^{III} species and phosphoric acid.

To find out mechanistic pathway for phosphoester cleavage and formation of enzyme-substrate adduct in solution as well as to reveal the nature of binding of pNPP to the Gd^{III} complex, we have recorded ESI-MS spectra in aqueous-DMF solution. The ESI-mass spectra of Gd^{III} complex show a prominent molecular ion peak at m/z 161.10, 460.17 and 587.30 in presence of pNPP as shown in Fig. S1. The mixture solution of Gd^{III} complex and pNPP of ratio 1 : 100, run after 10 min of mixing in aqueous DMF, showed the arising of new characteristics peaks with isotropic

distribution pattern. For the Gd^{III} complex an important peak detected at 587.30 can be ascribed to the cationic species, $[C_{10}H_{18}O_{14}NPGdNa]^+$ (theoretical $m/z = 587.10$) which suggests about the coordination of pNPP to Gd^{III} species in a monodentate fashion while another significant peak at m/z 460.17 indicates the production of active Gd^{III} species after releasing nitrophenolate species in solution. The base peak at m/z 161.10 (Theoret. $(C_6H_4NO_3Na)$ 161.14) is appeared for sodium salt of nitrophenolate compound. So, ESI-MS of the reaction mixture supports and consolidates the mechanistic aspect for phosphoester cleavage by Gd^{III} compound in aqueous DMF solvent mixture. In order to check the reactivity of the dinuclear gadolinium(III) core towards phosphatase activity we have compared our kinetics with some reported dinuclear zinc complexes in literature and given in Table 3.

Table 3. Kinetic parameters for the phosphoester hydrolysis of pNPP by **1** in aq. DMF at 25 °C

Complex	Substrate	V_{max} ($M s^{-1}$)	K_m (M)	K_{cat} (h^{-1})	Reference
1	pNPP	1.75×10^{-7}	5.37×10^{-4}	6.3	Present
$[Zn_2(CH_3HL_1)(CH_3COO)(H_2O)](PF_6)$	BDNPP	-	1.25×10^{-3}	3.85	36
$[Zn_2(CH_3L_3)(CH_3COO)_2](PF_6)$	BDNPP	-	1.89×10^{-2}	12.96	37
$[(Zn_2(IPCPMP)(CH_3COO))_2](PF_6)_2$	BDNPP	-	1.6×10^{-2}	2.304	38

*Std. Error for **1**, V_{max} ($M s^{-1}$) = 2.12×10^{-8} ; Std. Error for K_m (M) = 1.03×10^{-4} .

Conclusions

Herein, we report synthesis and phosphoester cleavage activity of a dimeric gadolinium acetate molecule. Single crystal X-ray diffraction study revealed that gadolinium(III) crystallizes in triclinic system with PT space group and each of the Gd^{III} centres in **1** adopts tricapped trigonal prism geometry. Lattice aqua molecules in **1** form cyclic tetrameric 8-membered water cluster and extended through $O\cdots H$ interactions in solid state using acetate linkers. The coordinated aqua molecules to Gd^{III} centres remain the key aspects behind the generation of hydroxide nucleophile through intermolecular proton transfer and coordinated hydroxide makes intramolecular nucleophilic attack on phosphorous atom in pNPP and cleaves phosphoester bond with production of phenolate ion and phosphoric acid in solution. This paper reports a novel addition of a dimeric gadolinium acetate which exhibits potential ability to mimic the active site of phosphatase enzyme with significant catalytic efficiency ($k_{obs} = 5.43 \times 10^{-4} \text{ min}^{-1}$) in absence of any base/basic buffer. Novelty of this Gd^{III} dimer lies not only in the existence of tetrameric water cluster but also the generation of coordinated aqua molecules to hydroxide in the catalytic route of hydrolytic phosphoester cleavage.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

High purity gadolinium(III) chloride (Sigma-Aldrich, USA), sodium acetate (E. Merck, India), disodium salt of (4-nitrophenyl)phosphate hexahydrate (Sigma-Aldrich, USA), and all reagents were purchased from the respective outlets and used as received.

Physical measurements :

Infrared spectrum (KBr) was recorded with a FTIR-8400S Shimadzu spectrophotometer in the range $400\text{--}3600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Ground state absorption was measured in a JASCO V-730 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Electrospray ionization (ESI) mass spectrum was recorded using a Q-tof-micro quadrupole mass spectrometer. The pH value of the solutions was measured in Systronics pH meter at room temperature. Elemental

analyses were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHN microanalyzer.

*Synthesis of $[Gd(OAc)_3(OH_2)_2]_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ (**1**) :*

A saturated aqueous solution (10 mL) of NaOAc was added drop-wise to an aqueous solution (10 mL) of $GdCl_3$ (0.263 g, 1 mM). The colourless solution was kept in reflux for 4 h at $120 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and filtered, and the supernatant liquid was kept in air for slow evaporation. After 12–15 days colourless crystals were appeared and isolated from the reactions solution. The crystalline compound was washed with hexane and dried *in vacuo* over silica gel indicator. Yield : 0.207 g (78.7% based on metal salt). Anal. Calcd. for $C_{12}H_{30}O_{18}Gd_2$ (**1**) : C, 18.55; H, 3.89. Found : C, 18.47; H, 3.85; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3401 (s), 1586 (s), 1498 (s), 1410(s), 1365 (m).

Crystal structure determination and refinement :

Single crystal X-ray diffraction data were collected in Bruker SMART APEX CCD diffractometer using graphite monochromated $Mo\text{-}K\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) at 100 K. The data were reduced using Crystal Clear suite, and the space group determination was done using Olex². The structure was resolved by direct method and refined by full-matrix least-squares procedures using the SHELXL-97 software package using OLEX² suite^{33,34}.

*Phosphatase activity of $[Gd(OAc)_3(H_2O)_2]_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ (**1**) :*

Disodium salt of (4-nitrophenyl)phosphate (pNPP) was employed as a convenient substrate to investigate the nature of hydrolytic cleavage of pNPP in aqueous DMF medium following a reported procedure³⁵. An initial screening of the hydrolytic tendency of the complex was followed until 2% formation of *p*-nitrophenolate (2 h) was reached, and then its kinetic data were collected. The hydrolysis rate of pNPP in the presence of the Gd^{III} complex was measured by an initial rate method keeping fixed the incremental band intensity in absorption at 415 nm due to the released *p*-nitrophenolate ion in aqueous DMF at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. For the wavelength scan, the spectrum was recorded by mixing a solution containing $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ pNPP and $1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ Gd^{III} complex for 2 h. The

values of A_{α} were determined by recording solution absorbance after 24 h and 48 h respectively. All measurements were performed in triplicate.

Supplementary data

Supplementary crystallographic data are available free of charge from The Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge, CB2 1EZ, UK (Fax : +44-1223-336033; E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or www: http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk) upon request, quoting deposition number CCDC 1551314.

Acknowledgment

The work was supported financially by Science & Engineering Research Board (SERB), a statutory body under DST, New Delhi under the Fast Track Scheme for Young Scientist (No. SB/FT/CS-088/2013 dtd. 21/05/2014).

References

- (a) A. E. Merbach and E. Toth, "The Chemistry of Contrast Agents in Medical Magnetic Resonance Imaging", Wiley, London, 2001; (b) R. B. Lauffer, *Chem. Rev.*, 1987, **87**, 901.
- (a) K. Binnemans, *Chem. Rev.*, 2009, **109**, 4283; (b) S. Pandya, J. Yu and D. Parker, *Dalton Trans.*, 2006, 2757.
- (a) A. Panagiotopoulos, T. F. Zafiroopoulos, S. P. Perlepes, E. Bakalbassis, I. Masson-Ramade, O. Kahn, A. Terzis and C. P. Raptopoulou, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1995, **34**, 4918; (b) A. Rizzi, R. Baggio, R. Calvo, M. T. Garland, O. Peña and M. Perec, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2001, **40**, 3623; (c) B. Biswas, P. Raghavaiah, N. Aliaga-Alcalde, J.-D. Chen and R. Ghosh, *Polyhedron*, 2010, **29**, 2716.
- G. R. J. Thatcher and R. Kluger, *Adv. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1989, **25**, 99.
- A. C. Hengge, Academic Press, New York, 1998, Vol. 1, pp. 517-542.
- (a) J. Aqvist, K. J. Kolmodin, Florian and A. Warshel, *Chem. Biol.*, 1999, **6**, R71; (b) D. Dey, A. De, H. R. Yadav, P. S. Guin, A. R. Choudhury, N. Kole and B. Biswas, *Chemistry Select.*, 2016, **01**, 1910; (c) D. Dey, S. Das and B. Biswas, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2016, **93**, 495; (d) B. Biswas, A. Al-Hunaiti, M. T. Räisänen, S. Ansalone, M. Leskelä, T. Repo, Y.-T. Chen, H.-L. Tsai, A. D. Naik, A. P. Railliet, Y. Garcia, R. Ghosh and N. Kole, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2012, 4479.
- (a) S. Admiraal and D. Herschlag, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **122**, 2145; (b) S. Pal, B. Chowdhury, M. Patra, M. Maji and B. Biswas, *Spectrochimica Acta, Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 2015, **144**, 148; (c) A. De, D. Dey, H. R. Yadav, M. Maji, V. Rane, R. M. Kadam, A. R. Choudhury and B. Biswas, *J. Chem. Sci.*, 2016, **128**, 1775.
- (a) A. Mildvan, *Proteins*, 1997, **4**, 401; (b) D. Dey, G. Kaur, A. Ranjani, L. Gyathri, P. Chakraborty, J. Adhikary, J. Pasan, D. Dhanasekaran, A. R. Choudhury, M. A. Akbarsha, N. Kole and B. Biswas, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2014, 3350.
- M. A. Sogorb and E. Vilanova, *Toxicol. Lett.*, 2002, **128**, 215.
- D. P. Dumas, S. R. Caldwell, J. R. Wild and F. M. Raushel, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1989, **264**, 19659.
- C. Jackson, P. D. Carr, H. K. Kim, J.-W. Liu, P. Herrald, N. Mitic, G. Schenk, C. A. Smith and D. L. Ollis, *Biochem. J.*, 2006, **397**, 501.
- C. J. Jackson, K. S. Hadler, P. D. Carr, A. J. Oakley, S. H.-C. Yip, G. Schenk and D. L. Ollis, *Acta Cryst.*, 2008, **F64**, 681.
- H. Yang, P. D. Carr, S. Y. McLoughlin, J. W. Liu, I. Horne, X. Qiu, C. M. Jeffries, R. J. Russell, J. G. Oakeshott and D. L. Ollis, *Protein Eng., Des. Sel.*, 2003, **16**, 135.
- M. M. Benning, H. Shim, F. M. Raushel and H. M. Holden, *Biochemistry*, 2001, **40**, 2712.
- M. M. Benning, J. Kuo, F. Raushel and M. Holden, *Biochemistry*, 1995, **34**, 7973.
- C. Jackson, H. K. Kim, P. D. Carr, J. W. Liu and D. L. Ollis, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta, Proteins Proteomics.*, 2005, **56**, 1752.
- G. Parkin, *Chem. Rev.*, 2004, **104**, 699.
- P. J. O'Brien and D. Herschlag, *Biochemistry*, 2002, **41**, 3207.
- S. A. Li, D. X. Yang, D. F. Li, J. Huang and W. X. Tang, *New J. Chem.*, 2002, **26**, 1831.
- C. Bazzicalupi, A. Bencini, E. Berni, A. Bianchi, V. Fedi, V. Fusi, C. Giorgi, P. Paoletti and B. Valtancoli, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1999, **38**, 4115.
- D. Yang, S. Li, D. Li, J. Xia, K. Yu and W. Tang, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2002, 4042.
- J. W. Chen, X. Y. Wang, Y. G. Zhu, J. Lin, X. L. Yang, Y. Z. Li, Y. Lu and Z. J. Guo, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2005, **44**, 3422.
- E. Kimura, I. Nakamura, T. Koike, M. Shionoya, Y. Kodama, T. Ikeda and M. Shiro, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1994, **116**, 4764.
- M. Livieri, F. Mancin and U. Tonellato, *J. Chin Chem. Commun.*, 2004, 2862.
- T. Koike, S. Kajitani, I. Nakamura, E. Kimura and M. Shiro, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1995, **117**, 1210.

De *et al.* : Coordinated aqua molecules mediated phosphoester cleavage activity *etc.*

26. J. Xia, Y. B. Shi, Y. Zhang, Q. Miao and W. X. Tang, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2003, **42**, 70.
27. (a) S. T. Hatscher and W. Urland, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2003, **42**, 2862; (b) M. C. Favas, D. L. Kepert, B. W. Skelton and A. H. White, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1980, 454; (c) L. Canadillas-Delgado, O. Fabelo, J. Cano, J. Pasan, F. S. Delgado, F. Lloret, M. Julve and C. Ruiz-Perez, *Cryst. Eng. Comm.*, 2009, **11**, 2131.
28. P. Hendry and A. M. Sargeson, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1990, **29**, 92.
29. P. Hendry and A. M. Sargeson, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1986, **39**, 1177.
30. S. Benkovic and L. Dunikoski, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **93**, 1526.
31. (a) Y. Murakami and J. Sunamoto, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1971, **44**, 1827; (b) T. Fife and M. Pujari, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **110**, 7790.
32. (a) F. Mancin, P. Scrimina and P. Tecilla, *Chem. Progress in Artificial Metallonucleases Commun.*, 2012, **48**, 5545; (b) N. H. Williams, B. Takasaki, M. Wall and J. Chin, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1999, **32**, 485; (c) Y. Ren, J. Lu, B. Cai, D. Shi, H. Jiang, J. Chen, D. Zheng and B. Liu, *Dalton Trans.*, 2011, **40**, 1372.
33. CrystalClear 2.0, Rigaku Corporation, Tokyo, Japan.
34. G. M. Sheldrick, *Acta Cryst.*, 2008, **A64**, 112.
35. M. Garai, D. Dey, H. R. Yadav, A. R. Choudhury, N. Kole and B. Biswas, *Polyhedron*, 2017, **129**, 114.
36. K. E. Dalle, L. J. Daumann, G. Schenk, R. P. McGeary, L. R. Hanton and L. R. Gahan, *Polyhedron*, 2017, **52**, 1336.
37. L. J. Daumann, K. E. Dalle, G. Schenk, R. P. McGeary, P. V. Bernhardt, D. L. Ollis and L. R. Gahan, *Dalton Trans.*, 2012, **41**, 1695.
38. M. Jarenmark, E. Csapo, J. Singh, S. Wockel, E. Farkas, F. Meyer, M. Haukka and E. Nordlander, *Dalton Trans.*, 2010, **39**, 8183.

